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Languages in contemporaneity

In the midst of scientific efforts to overcome Coronavirus pandemic, which has been drastically affecting the world population since 2020, a topic addressed in the latest issue published by **Revista Letras Raras (RLR)** (v. 10, n. 4, 2021), we also saw the imminent war in Eastern Europe at the beginning of this year. Besides that, in the Brazilian context, the current government intends to format a population that does not study, does not discuss and does not question. Thus, in this time of conflict, **RLR** resists the conflicts established and goes against the government, inviting its readers to critically reflect on the current and urgent problems, which are discussed in this edition.

Among such a pandemic, a negationist wave, and a war (and so many others that have been going on for a long time and that are ignored or normalised), this first issue of 2022, entitled *Languages in contemporaneity*, inaugurates the eleventh year of **RLR**. Hence, we present reflections and studies about themes that should be brought to light for discussions and, in some cases, possibilities for resolutions, thus bringing sparks of hope for our days.

Thereby, in this edition, organised by professors Alain-Philippe Durand, from the University of Arizona, Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz, from the Federal University of Campina Grande, and Maria Rennally Soares da Silva, from the State University of Paraíba, there are nine papers in the fields of *Discourse Analysis, Applied Linguistics, Literature, Translation*, in addition to four essays in the areas of *Translation, Linguistics, Discourse Analysis* and *Literature*. There are also two important translations of texts originally published in French, based on studies of *Linguistics* and *Literature*, besides nine texts of artistic creation. This edition of plural themes represents the opening of **RLR** to the diversity of discussions about *Languages in contemporaneity*.

The texts presented come from authors of Brazilian and foreign universities, such as: Regional University of the Northwest of the State of Rio Grande do Sul (UNIJUÍ), University of Brasília (UnB), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), Catholic University of Pernambuco (UNICAP), Federal University of Bahia (UFBA), Federal University of Sergipe (UFS), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), State University

of Ceará (UECE), Federal Rural University of Pernambuco (UFRPE), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Maranhão (IFMA), Federal Institute Farroupilha (IFFAR), University of Minho (Uminho), University of Aveiro (UA), University of Cergy-Pontoise (UCP), and University of Montpellier.

The artistic creation texts made of poems and short stories were written by Brazilian authors coming from the Federal University of ABC (UFABC), Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), Federal University of Fronteira Sul (UFFS), State University of Campinas (UNICAMP), State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), and Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL).

In this edition, the first of nine papers is entitled **Political-affective scenarios of black women in post-colonial contexts: an intersectional analysis of Buchi Emecheta's works**. It is authored by scholars Maria Elizabeth Peregrino Souto Maior Mendes and Ana Clara Velloso Borges Pereira, from the Federal University of Paraíba. Based on intersectional theories and gender studies, this research presents some important reflections on the oppressions that affect Nigerian women portrayed by the writer studied, identifying the stigmas imposed on African women in the novels *As alegrias da maternidade* (1979) and *Cidadã de Segunda Classe* (1974).

Still from the perspective of women's spaces in societies, but now, from the perspective of Discourse Analysis, the paper **Conservatism and feminism: representations of women in Mafalda Comic Strips** is written by Rafaela Santos Rosa and Fabio Elias Verdiani Tfouni, from the Federal University of. The authors analyse the discursive practices in Mafalda's comic strips, by the cartoonist Quino, discussing the actuality of these graphic works, besides the problem that develops from the ideological apparatus of the family and its place in social relations.

The third paper, entitled **From "imbecile" to "peace of the lord" effects of sense in a religious live from the subject-position of pastor** is presented by Dalexon Sérgio da Silva and Maria do Carmo Gomes Pereira Cavalcanti, from the Catholic University of Pernambuco. Based on Discourse Analysis, it discusses a video in which an evangelical spiritual guide addresses his public with a religious discourse of peace, however he did not realise the beginning of the recording, thus producing antagonistic utterances, pejoratively describing his wife some moments ago. These reflections make us understand the presence of two antagonistic discursive formations, captured by the film camera, recording different effects of meaning.

Still in the field of Discourse Analysis, but from a critical and decolonial perspective, the fourth paper is entitled **A critical analysis on English textbooks and literature as an alternative resource for decolonial education**, by Fernanda Mota-Pereira, from the Federal University of Bahia. The author presents a critical analysis of two textbooks for teaching English as a foreign language, namely: “Interchange” and “Breakthrough”. Reading this paper leads us to conclude that, in the analysed books, there is an emphasis on communicative competence to the detriment of plural aims, which could be directed to expand critical thinking and social awareness.

The fifth paper, entitled **English language and the internationalisation of Higher Education: a comparative analysis of two institutions from BRICS countries**, is authored by Tamara Angélica Brudna da Rosa, from the Federal Institute Farroupilha, by Maria Cristina de Araújo, from the Regional University of the Northwest of the State of Rio Grande do Sul, by Kléber Aparecido da Silva, from the University of Brasília, and by Vilton Soares de Souza, from the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Maranhão. This research deals with the place of English in the internationalisation of Higher Education, analysing documents and social representations of two universities in BRICS countries, one in southern Brazil and the other in Eurasian Russia. It shows that English is crossed by questions of internationalisation, while the institutional policies for learning English in both communities present discrepancies in relation to the interests of the intended internationalisation.

In the field of Brazilian Literature, the sixth paper **Cheesy Literature: memory in the novels *Nunca houve tanto fim como agora* and *O mendigo que sabia de cor os adágios de Erasmo de Rotterdam***, by Evandro Affonso Ferreira, is presented by Maria Regina Soares Azevedo de Andrade and Juliane Vargas Welter, from the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte. They investigate the device of memory in contemporary Brazilian literature, based on the novels *O mendigo que sabia de cor os adágios de Erasmo de Rotterdam* (2012) and *Nunca houve tanto fim como agora* (2017), both written by Evandro Affonso Ferreira. Hence, it enables the understanding that memory can be used to claim other versions of History, providing voice to historically invisible individuals and narratives.

Following that, the reader will find the seventh paper. **The lyrics of the songs *Coco livre* and *Taquarulua* - poetry, culture and imaginary**, by Juliana Santana de Almeida and Nivaldo Monteiro Camilo da Silva Bodnar, from the Federal University of Tocantins. The authors present us with an analysis of the lyrics of the songs *Coco Livre*, from the musical album *Brasís: as canções*

e o povo (1998), by Genésio Tocantins, and of *Taquarulua*, from the musical album *Taquarulua* (2009), by Dorivã, thus exploring the words that relate to the local culture, poetry and the Tocantins state imaginary.

In the field of translation, the eighth paper is entitled **Intersemiotic mismatches in memes: a study of machine translation output from English into Portuguese**, by Pedro Rezende Simões and Thiago Blanch Pires, from the University of Brasília. The text analyses automatic translations of memes situated in multimodal contexts and social networks, relating text-image in English memes, automatically translated into Portuguese, highlighting the intersemiotic incompatibilities of this category of translation.

Concluding the papers section, **Translating the defeat of dreams: *Torto Arado*, a stunning journey through the open ruts of Latin America** is authored by Felipe Cammaert, from the University of Aveiro. The author comments on translation aspects of the novel *Torto Arado* (2019) by Itamar Vieira Junior, a work that tells the story of a community of African Brazilian workers on a farm in the state of Bahia.

Opening the essays section, **Between translation and literary adaptation: perspectives in the study of children's and youth literature** is presented by Yessy Villavicencio Simón, Andrea Martins Lameirão Mateus, Márcio Araújo de Melo Araújo de Melo, and Valéria da Silva Medeiros, from the Federal University of Tocantins. The essay presents a reflection on the concepts of intertextuality in the process of translation and literary adaptation, presenting aspects related to the practices of reading adapted literary texts that might contribute to the education of children and youth readers.

The second essay **Critical multimodal literacy in a decolonial perspective**, by Adriana dos Santos Pereira, from the State University of Ceará, problematizes her own Master's research. The author reflects on what she considers as gaps about the image of women in the analysed corpus, having a decolonial perspective as a basis for discussion.

Afterwards, the third essay is entitled **A boy, a tree: social representations and repercussions for literature teaching**, by Nataniel Mendes, from the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Maranhão and the University of Minho. The essay discusses the teaching of literature in Brazilian public schools, analysing a report aired on a television program. And, finally, the literary essay **Words or expressions that were lost [or not] in the midst of writing: An essay on writing**, by Ronaldo Luís Goulart Campello and Ursúla Rosa da

Silva, from the Federal University of Pelotas, presents considerations of a wandering teacher who reflects on the act of writing.

Accordingly to the scope and policy of this journal, we also present the translation of a paper by professors Catherine Boré and Catherine Bosredon, from the University of Cergy-Pontoise, entitled *La phrase selon les brouillons: un trajet entre l'oral et l'écrit*, which is translated into Brazilian Portuguese as **A frase segundo os rascunhos: um trajeto entre o oral e o escrito** [The sentence according to the drafts: a path between the oral and the written]. The translation was developed by Kall Anne Sheyla Amorim Braga, from the Federal Rural University of Pernambuco, and presents reflections on students' point of view about language, based on drafts.

The second translation is of a chapter by the researcher Brigitte Louichon, professor and scholar at the University of Montpellier, entitled *Les rayons imaginaires de nos bibliothèques intérieures*, translated into Brazilian Portuguese as **As prateleiras imaginárias de nossas bibliotecas interiores** [The imaginary shelves of our inner libraries]. The translation was made by Emerson Patrício de Moraes Filho, from the Federal University of Campina Grande. The text presents the metaphor of a library as a representation of the collection of knowledge acquired in readings carried out throughout life, also bringing testimonies from readers that attest to the accuracy of the concept presented.

The poems published in this first edition are: **Arte: refúgio daqueles que ainda sonham**, by Tom Menezes, from the Federal University of ABC; **Extinto**, by Maurício Fontana Filho, from the Regional University of the Northwest of the State of Rio Grande do Sul; **O Lobo e a Lua**, by José D'Assunção Barros, from the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro; **Eu, você...**, by Adriana dos Santos Pereira, from the State University of Ceará; **Disputa**, by Monique Comin Losina, from the Federal University of Fronteira Sul; **O trezinho do mineiro**, by Teófilo Teles Pereira de Arvelos, from the State University of Campinas; and **Versos drásticos**, by Adson Luan Duarte Vilasboas Seba, from the State University of Mato Grosso. As for the short stories, we have: **Os invisíveis**, by Wellington Amancio da Silva, from the Federal University of Alagoas; and the anthology of short stories: **'A ficção do instante'**, **'Miopia - um conto hierático'** and **'Boneca de Pano'**, by Yvisson Gomes dos Santos, from the Federal University of Alagoas.

Dear reader, this first edition of 2022, which can also be read by its QR Code¹, presents papers that insight different reflections in the area of *Letters, Discourse Analysis, Applied Linguistics, Literature, Translation*, in short, *Languages in contemporaneity*.

Therefore, we begin the year 2022 by wishing that any conflicts, wars, denialism and so many other evils that plague us for now, give way to dialogues, reflections, discussions, and scientific advancement, so that we can live in societies more just and full of peace. That is our will.

Have a great reading!

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Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral.

¹ See the posts in our social networks: <https://instagram.com/revistalettrasraras> and <https://fb.com/revistalettrasraras>